

Art Doc Viz - Interactive Visualization of Artist Documentation

Luna Nane*, Isa Teichmann**

reclaim.hypotheses.org

<https://www.art-doc-archive.net/>

Abstract

Over the past two decades, digital archiving and building interfaces to access digital archives has been a major challenge at the intersection of computer sciences, arts and humanities. In our project, we approach social media data and website data from artists as a way of self-documentation that we want to archive and bring in context. In this text, We outline the making of Art Doc Viz, an interactive visualization that builds on an open source and machine-learning-based data pipeline designed to bring arbitrary amounts of artists' self-documented work from different sources (for example Instagram and websites) into a visualization structure that makes it accessible interactively and in 3D, and that makes relations between the artists' documentations visible. This is achieved by using a series of AI tools like entity recognition and image recognition and UMAP as a clustering algorithm. Finally, the visualization uses advanced 3D graphics to enable the user to explore the visualization in an intuitive way.

Keywords: Interactive Data-Visualization, Digital Archives, Human-Computer Interaction, Computer Graphics, Media Arts, Art History

1. Introduction

Art Doc Archive as a project was initiated with the idea that artists' self-documentations are widely scattered on the internet, partly in all types of personal artist websites and partly in social media, that is, basically corporate platforms. All of these media are not necessarily reliable to last forever, as personal websites require maintenance and paid servers and, in the past, corporate

Luna Nane is a trans-identifying artist and creative technologist in the field of interactive media. Since 2011, she has been working freelance with creative technologies, interactive and media arts, data visualization, procedural generation and AI.

**Isa Teichmann is a transfemme computer engineering student. She has a background in social studies. She works freelance as a speaker and educator for queer topics, and is also a research assistant and programmer.

platforms have proven to be not very long-lasting, with users abandoning platforms or platforms shutting down entirely. For art historians, researchers, art institutions and perhaps the artists themselves, such artists' self-documentations are valuable and worthy of being preserved for the future. This gave rise to the Art Archive project and we started working as a team in different directions that would cover the subject. The three directions are called Art Doc Parser, Art Doc Web and Art Doc Viz. The first two directions here, Art Doc Parser and Art Doc Web, covered the extraction of descriptions of artworks from websites and the archiving of the websites, whether that be personal pages or social media. This is done by using open-source software that could record the web content in a database structure and a front-end that could play back this web content again. To bring the artists self-documentations into relation to each other and to make everything accessible in an intuitive way, the prototype of ArtDocViz was created. ArtDocViz is an interactive data-visualization.

2. Interactive data visualization

Lets have a look at why we used interactive data-visualization in this project. Data-visualization itself has been a very active research field and community in the past three decades. This began with the early and important works of Edward Tufte, who came up with principles for how visual entities like dots and lines can be used to make data visible in clean and concise ways [1]. Thus, data-visualization became essential to aid understanding of scientific data. Experts in data-visualizations emerged and it became an interdisciplinary field, as people from all disciplines started joining this community. In computer science, interactive data-visualization gained in importance because of how it could enable the exploration of large amounts of data, something that is difficult with static images as used in traditional data-visualization. The interface to explore the data has increasingly attracted the attention of researchers and data-visualization practitioners. The more we gather large amounts of high-dimensional data, the more we run into the problem of how to actually work with this data, how to understand it and how to explore it in a way that is intuitive for humans. Interactive data-visualization is also often referred to as a way to approach data that enables finding unexpected patterns or things you only realize exist when you are actually able to find it. It is also worth noting that an open-source community of data-visualization practitioners evolved in the 2010s around the javascript library d3.js. This library enabled many users to come up with interactive visualizations for the web [2]. While a lot of these data-visualization projects where useful in their domain, they were largely still visualized in 2D space. Interactive visualizations using 3D space remain comparably rare even today, and the mostly require custom programming, as a designated 3D data-visualization library does not exist. However, interactive 3D visualizations can have an advantage over 2D space, since the human brain is used to understanding objects in 3D space. And being able to rotate and zoom around in large quantities of data also helps us to understand it intuitively.

3. Interactive visualization of archives and image archives

Research into and attempts to build software and hardware interfaces to visualize archives – and especially image archives – have been of ongoing interest since the early 2000s with touch-screen interfaces to visualize personal photo collections [3], to research projects setting foundations for digital libraries [4] and, later in the 2010s different implementations of large media environments that build artworks around the exploration of image archives, such as the works of Sarah Kenderdine as early as 2012 [5]. Many more similar image-archive applications and people working in the field followed in the years after that, for example, the Collectionscope open-source software engine, which focuses on the visualization of museum collections [6].

4. Building the information space: t-SNE and UMAP

One of the big challenges working with large archives in this way is the question of how to build the visual information space. Basically, how can the data be arranged in 2D or 3D space, and what interaction methods can be applied in order to access the data in a meaningful way? A major challenge here is that, in a lot of archives, every data-point, whether a book, document, painting or any other medium, often stands only for itself. Typical ways of accessing this data, for example in classic library software, include searching by author or topic and retrieving a list of entries from the software, which is a very narrow view of the entire archive. Applying the principles of interactive data-visualization that enables free exploration of the data in a sort of information space, however, requires an entirely different approach. This problem is a general one and also applies to any type of large data set. Where are the patterns and the similarity, and what does the data look like from a bird’s-eye perspective? This question has been addressed by the concept of clustering data and dimensional-reduction techniques, but also tree-based approaches of mapping data. These algorithms can find patterns in data and put it into a format that enables visualization. Fan, for example, used a hyperbolic tree-based approach [7], and Eller used NJ-trees to map different image data in space, so that similar images would be close to each other [8]. In 2008, t-SNE was introduced by Van der Maaten [9] and became one of the most-utilized general ways of clustering data. The t-SNE algorithm in particular has been shown to achieve very good results in arranging data-points as points in 2D or 3D space with proximity to each other indicating a sort of similarity in the data. In 2018, UMAP was published and was able to yield better results for many use-cases [10]. Both UMAP and t-SNE have been used as the basis for interactive visualizations of art and image archives. In the 2016 TED Talk “Every piece of art you’ve ever wanted to see -- up close and searchable” [11], Google’s Art and Culture Lab revealed some of their work on working with large image archives being visualized using t-SNE. Part of this work is accessible online as an interactive archive visualization of 623 partner collections represented in a landscape like a 3D t-SNE image cloud

[12]. In 2017, Refik Anadol created an immersive interactive installation featuring a t-SNE visualization of the SALT archive in Istanbul with the artwork “Archive Dreaming” [13]. At that time, other similar projects were also seen, like the work Audun M. Øygard did for the National Museum of Norway [14], which showed a t-SNE cloud of the museum’s archive as a web-based experience. Other applications that have been using UMAP as a core for interactive visualizations, for example, are the ESM Metagenomic Atlas that shows 600 million predicted protein structures in a breathtaking pattern [15]. Another example is the Exploring Fashion MNIST application, which shows the fashion images benchmark dataset as a 3D image cloud using UMAP [16]. Orion Search is also a project that maps scientific papers in relationship to each other and allows for papers to be discovered. And then there is PixPlot, a tool that lets the user browse the Meserve-Kunhardt Collection of historical photographs, designed by Yale’s Digital Humanities lab [17].

5. Classifying images

In the aforementioned Ted talk, Amit Sood also talks about the solution for another problem, namely, how can we get a hold of the data from the images that would enable the clustering algorithm to actually find patterns? In many archives we already have metadata associated to the images or documents, but we often don’t have the associated meta-data, or not enough to make a meaningful clustering. It is also important to understand, that t-SNE and UMAP rely on a more dense and abstract representation of the image to relate image to each other, like for example word embedding or more abstract representation of the images. So to say a sort of meaning. It needs this at least for higher resolution images. It can not look at the images by itself or at least that wouldn’t be enough for the the algorithm to sort the images in relation to each other. A practical – but also questionable solution – is to use another machine-learning algorithm to get the description of the image from the AI. This naturally brings into play the problem of bias in image-recognition software, and in some use cases this might be problematic and debatable. Nevertheless, it has been shown that obtaining the word-embedding from an image to use it with t-SNE or UMAP is a solution that works, at least on a large scale and for the bird’s-eye perspective. What we ultimately do is create a map of the archive, and there will be an AI bias in the map, which might be OK or not, but we have no other way of classifying large amounts of images.

6. Classifying text

Our visualization also wants to do the clustering according to website text and captions of social media posts. As these texts can be of arbitrary size, one interesting approach is to also use machine learning to reduce the text to a handful of entities – like names and personas, locations and organizations – to get a clearer clustering result when using the text instead of the images. This

Figure 1: Flowchart visualization of the different stages of the data-pipeline

can be achieved via Named Entity Recognition (NER), which is a subtask of Natural Language Processing (NLP). Several different pre-trained models exist and can be used for free.

7. Overview Methods

The following chapter aims to provide the reader with the knowledge needed to understand the open-source pipeline we built and eventually use it for their own project, while understanding why it was built and how we came to make the choices we did. We also want to acknowledge that this is a prototype and a basic backbone, which, while it works, is still incomplete and imperfect. We encourage active participation in the discussion and also, of course, participation in the coding by extending the git repository ¹. A flowchart visualization of the individual stages of the pipeline is outlined in Figure 1 and may aid the reader in following up on the writing, as every chapter is depicted as a stage in the diagram, with example data.

8. Data input

For our prototype visualization, we asked a small, selected group of artists to donate their Instagram data. They were asked to manually use the official way of exporting their data from Instagram and to send it to us. After receiving the data and working with our own, we noticed early on that Instagram exported

¹<https://codeberg.org/artdocarchive/artdocviz>

from Instagram with JSON is very inconsistent in its formatting. Instagram has perhaps undergone many API changes over the years and, as a result, how the data is labeled and saved for export is extremely inconsistent. As a consequence, we needed to build a pre-parser that takes into account a lot of special cases. For example, in many of the exports from different users, the image paths were not correctly referenced. Some users had all images in `/media/other`, while JSON was referencing it in `media/posts/<date>`. As a solution, we had to build a parser that would detect these errors in the data and implement fallback paths based on our observation. But since we have only worked with less than ten Instagram accounts, there is no way we can tell whether we considered all necessary fallback cases. So, adapting the pre-parser or writing an own one would eventually be necessary if errors appear in this early stage of simply converting from JSON to CSV. For this pre-parsing step to work, we prepared a folder that contains each data export of the artists as an individual folder with the name of the person as the folder name. This is the input data for the pre-parser.

9. Pre-parsing

While, in this first prototype, we worked mostly with data from Instagram, the pipeline should not only be designed with one type of data in mind, but for any data that can be obtained in a very simple first format and that consists of a collection of images and/or text. Ideally, the text and images should relate to each other, like Instagram posts, where the description text is below the image, but this is not an absolute must. While usually we would use data that has both images and text, the pipeline would also work for data with only images and data with only text. To enable any data to enter the pipeline, we decided to implement a pre-parsing step for the Instagram data that would transfer the relatively difficult to access JSON format into a simple CSV format. Our pre-parsing step would format the data in a format where each row contains the following data, whereas columns are separated by semicolons: image filename; user; description; date with each row representing one data-point (in our case an Instagram post), and each column in the row representing one of these dimensions: image filename pointing to a folder where the images are exported to by the pre-parser, user as the Instagram user or author of post, description as the text of the post, data as the timestamp of the post. It should be easy for any other input data that fits roughly this structure to be parsed into this simple format with a custom parser. In the case of the Instagram data, we built a prototyping pre-parser based on the visual programming language vvvv beta, which comes with a very good solution to experimentally work with JSON data. The pre-parser also extracts the images from the folders provided by the Instagram export, resizes them to 256x256 pixel, renames them to a simple index with 10 digits (e.g., “000000001.jpg”, “000000002.jpg” and so on), saves them to a folder called “/images” and stores an extra file with the original width and height of the images in pixels in a simple csv format for later use.

10. Data analysis

In order to find good ways to cluster the data-points for the interactive visualization, we tried various algorithmic and machine-learning-based ways of finding more differentiated data in the existing data. Some of these use image recognition on the images and some of them try to find entities, like personas and places in the text data. The initial CSV data we produce in the pre-parsing step then gets extended by additional columns for each of the analysis steps. Below, we look at the different methods we applied in detail. All the methods are summarized in one ipynb file, which can be opened with google colab or jupyter notebook and can be used to process the data all at once. The simplest text analysis was scanning for hashtags. Hashtags are marked with a “#” symbol before the tag word and are therefore easy to extract using regular expressions. The other data analysis methods are outline in more detail in the following chapters.

11. Entity recognition

We applied entity recognition using the MIT-licensed spaCy library. SpaCy is an open-source library for Natural Language Processing (NLP) in Python. It is specifically designed to efficiently process large amounts of text and provides a wide range of functions for tokenization, POS tagging, parsing, named entity recognition (NER), and text classification. The entity recognition takes the description text as input and tries to find entities according to the following categories: person, organization, facility, national political or religious groups, geographic location, product, event, work of art and date. This is correspondingly simple to use, however the internal process consists of several sub-steps and is relatively complex. First, spaCy tokenizes the input text – dividing it into words and sub-words. Then a grammatical analysis called part-of-speech (POS) tagging tags every token as a noun, verb, etc. Finally, dependency parsing identifies the relationship between the tokens (for example, the subject-verb-object relationship). The NER is executed based on this. This is the procedure that many NLP models use for their NER. We decided on the accuracy-focused version of spaCy called `en_core_web_trf`, as it’s easy to use, lightweight, fast and has a NER accuracy rate of 89.8 percent on the OntoNotes 5.0 corpora. Also, the trained model is available in 24 languages, which gives us the possibility of extending the project to other languages. Additionally, spaCy also provides the option of customizing the pre-trained model for any use case. With word vectors, the model can be trained on a specific list of known entities. For our project, for example, we were able to model word vectors of known museums, known artists, etc. allowing us to improve our NER in the future.

12. Image recognition based on ImageNet

Our first attempt to make sense of the images with machine learning was by using `resnext101_32x8d`, a very often-applied Image Recognition model based

on TensorFlow. This image-recognition library was trained on ImageNet, which means it has the limitation of only being able to recognize 1000 categories of objects. While this is the largest open dataset with existing pre-trained models, it is better to interpret it as a science benchmark for new Image Recognition models than as a standard set for multiple use cases. For an image, the algorithm would return multiple object descriptions and corresponding probabilities of how likely the results are true. With only 1000 possible categories, we noticed early on that this would give us results in our use case that were not very accurate. We are hoping to interpret an arbitrary amount of images made by artists in a way that is suitable to use with the UMAP clustering algorithm. Therefore, the content of our images doesn't easily fit into the 1000 categories of ImageNet, which is more a generalized list of things that we find in the world, like dogs, cats and plants or jackets – objects basically. Even though it is impressive, and the resnext101 is able to differentiate between several dog breeds for example, our use case rather wants to see what actually happens in an image, not so much which objects can be found in it. In theory, it would be possible to train TensorFlow with arbitrary data on new categories for many different use cases. With enough ethically collected and classified data and human resources, this would allow us to train our own model that could have more art-related categories like 'landscape photography' or 'self-portraits', for example. This approach would allow us to add one more standardized marker to each entry, which would increase the comparability of the entries. In the end, however, this approach is always as limited as the number of categories used and ultimately expects every input picture to be classifiable using the categories it was trained with. Therefore, it is more image classification than open image recognition. Nevertheless, within the limitations of this project, this method is viable.

13. Image recognition based on text2prompt

Realizing early on that the image recognition based on resnext101 or any other pre-trained model is a very general one that doesn't work that well for our use case or would need some extensive additional training – a task that would have been out of the scope of the project – we tried to come up with a better solution. It was purely coincidental that text2prompt was released at that time. The git repository of text2prompt doesn't mention use cases for image recognition, but it is designed to extract possible prompts from images that can then be used in image generation, for example, using Stable Diffusion. So, it works like a reverse version of Stable Diffusion. For the reader who is not familiar with image generation AI like Stable Diffusion, these programs work by generating an image based on a text input of the user, and this text input is called a 'prompt'. For example, a text like "an elephant on the moon, painting by Moebius" would produce quite a good result with an image that looks like an elephant on the moon painted in the style of the famous comic artist Moebius. Playing around with that, we noticed that this library is a much better fit for our use case, at least in part. This is because, in the first part of its prompt, it almost always very precisely describes in a full sentence what is seen in the

image – which works most of the time quite well for the kinds of images artists upload. The second part of the prompt, however, gives additional description of the style of the image, for example, the kind of painting style or what artists could have painted it. We noticed that this part is not useful for us, or it even feels overreaching to interpret an artist’s work in an Instagram post by imposing another artist’s style onto it. So, we started working with only the first part of the prompt, which is a relatively neutral and usable description of what is happening in the image. This already resulted in a significant contrast compared to the ImageNet-based resnext101 model we used first, which can only distinguish between 1,000 categories and tries to find them in an image. We were therefore quite satisfied with the result and our finding of img2prompt.

14. 3D clustering with UMAP

UMAP is a machine-learning algorithm – more precisely, a general-purpose manifold learning and dimensional reduction algorithm – that is used for clustering data in 2D or 3D space. It is extensively documented and has many helpful examples for all kinds of use cases, like image archives, word embeddings, genetic data, animal data or even sound. In short, what it does for us and why we use it can be described as follows: we can give UMAP all kinds of high-dimensional data and it would apply dimensional reduction to it and output a position vector for each data-point. Plotting all those position vectors for all the data-points in 3D space would result in a visualization where similar data-points are in proximity to each other. This similarity term we use here is a very relative one, since how the positions are calculated depends a lot on the input data and the parameters of the algorithm.

15. Bag-of-Words algorithm

Since all of the dimensions of the input data are different forms of text, we looked at one UMAP example to start with for the clustering, and modified it to work well with our data. In the example “Document embedding using UMAP” [18], newspaper articles are clustered by using the bag-of-words algorithm. Our data is actually quite well suited to working with this approach, as, for each dimension – e.g., description text, image recognition result, hashtags, entities etc. - we have an arbitrary number of words per data-point. The algorithm works in a way so that word order in the text doesn’t count. In a first step, the words get cleaned up and English stop words (the, and, etc.) and empty spaces get removed. Finally, with the remaining words, a word document matrix is constructed where the rows represent each data-point and the columns contain each word with the number representing how often it occurs.

16. Applying the data to UMAP

With the UMAP clustering, we effectively want to produce a cloud of 3D points, where each point relates to a data-point in our data. For our final vi-

sualization, we actually produced six different point clouds, each with another dimension of the data as input. In the visualization, the user can switch between these point clouds, depending on which clustering makes the most sense for the user. It is like having different perspectives of the data: the perspective of having it clustered according to hashtags only, but also all the other perspectives – like the description or the images recognition results. Theoretically, a combination of these dimensions is possible, too. Since we use the bag-of-words algorithm, we can combine multiple dimensions in the data by simply concatenating the strings of different dimensions. For example, by putting image-recognition results and hashtags together. For simplicity, we focused on producing the clouds for the following data dimensions: full description as written by post author, extracted hashtags, combined entity-recognition results, image recognition with resnext101 results, image-recognition results with img2prompt, redacted image-recognition results with img2prompt (by using only the first part before the comma of the img2text result). The UMAP algorithm has several parameters, which we left relatively untouched from the initial example. We use a “hellinger” metric for all clouds, but there are a lot of possible different metric options that change the result of the clustering and eventually some would work better, but we left it here and felt that it gives good results. There is also a parameter called `min_df`, which specifies which words are kept depending on their overall occurrence in all data-points. So, for example, `min_df = 2` would keep words that appear 2 times in all the data-points. Depending on how sparse the data is, it made sense to us to adjust this parameter. For example, the combined entity-recognition results had very few words in the word-document matrix compared to the other dimensions, so it made sense to make words influence the clustering already when they appear more than 2 times. For the dimensions with a larger number of words, we used `min_df = 5`. Finally, each of the 6 UMAPs gets exported by the python script as a comma-separated csv file with X, Y and Z coordinates. There are exactly as many positions in this file as data-points in the input file, so that each point in 3D space can be mapped to the respective data-point.

17. ArtDocViz – about the visualization

Finally, we bring all the generated and collected data into an interactive 3D visualization. In this visualization, the user can switch between a cluster mode, which shows the data-points as spheres and is designed for better comprehension of the topology of the UMAP, and an image mode, which shows the images of each data-point in 3D space. Each data-point can be clicked, and then a sidebar reveals the data associated to the point. To examine areas of interest or data-points of interest in relation to the other data-points, it is possible to switch between the different clustering types, which shows an animation of the points transitioning between the cluster types. This way, the user can see where certain points stand in relation to each other when clustering with different cluster types. Let’s recall that we applied the UMAP algorithm to cluster the

Figure 2: Figure 2: Art Doc Viz in cluster view showing the umap based on img2prompt results and all search terms for the word "gallery" highlighted as black circles. The righthand panel displays the selected data-point's content, the left-hand panel lets you select between view modes and different clustering modes.

data in six different ways, each sorting according to another aspect of the data (see chapter Applying the data to UMAP).

The visualization also features a search bar and a search term can be typed in there. It then highlights all points in the 3D visualization that contain the search term with a circle around them, so the user can navigate there using the 3D navigation. The application is developed with vvv gamma and exported as an executable for Windows.

18. Conclusion

In the three-month timeline for this project, we managed to get three artists to donate their Instagram data to work with as part of the project. A relative small number given our effort of writing to a lot of people in our networks, but this kind of manual data export of data that users had to go through was quite a hurdle and some people wanted to participate but in the end sent us the wrong data. In total, the dataset consists out of about 2,700 Instagram posts with associated pictures. Thus, our sample size is still limited. And yet, we can still say that we accomplished the most important task for us here: to get meaningful clusters from the final visualization. It seems that the img2prompt redacted approach in particular yields very good results, and clusters are concentrated around actual real similar images. In addition, using clustering by hashtag works great as long as hashtags are present. Some clustering types might perform better with bigger sample sizes, but didn't perform so well with our sample size, resulting in unspecific distribution of points in 3D space by the UMAP

algorithm. Nevertheless, for some data-points, these clustering types make sense and reveal nearby points that are somewhat similar. It is also important to not only look at the pictures for similarity, which is why we introduced the cluster mode that does not show the images but only 3d spheres for the points. For example, when clustering by description, this makes a lot of sense, as artists do not necessarily describe the image, but do write down the content of the post. Therefore, we can compare actual content and be even more differentiated by using the entity-recognition-based UMAP. This one, however, seems to need a higher sample size of the data, since it is relatively rare that entities get extracted, and finding similarity among a smaller amount of data needs a higher sample size. What is more, the visualization is very basic yet playful and thus enables real exploration. There are a lot of ideas for the future, for example, to also implement a timeline and have the clusters change over time. We have not worked with the meta-data of the post authors or users at all so far. But network data could also be implemented and might reveal more relations between the artists and the content.

References

- [1] Edward R Tufte. The visual display of quantitative information. *The Journal for Healthcare Quality (JHQ)*, 7(3):15, 1985.
- [2] Scott Murray. *Interactive data visualization for the web: an introduction to designing with D3*. " O'Reilly Media, Inc.", 2017.
- [3] Baback Moghaddam, Qi Tian, Neal Lesh, Chia Shen, and Thomas S Huang. Visualization and user-modeling for browsing personal photo libraries. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 56(1-2):109–130, 2004.
- [4] Harald Reiterer. New forms of Human-Computer Interaction for Visualizing Information. In Andreas Kerren, Catherine Plaisant, and John T. Stasko, editors, *Information Visualization*, volume 10241 of *Dagstuhl Seminar Proceedings (DagSemProc)*, pages 1–4, Dagstuhl, Germany, 2010. Schloss Dagstuhl – Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik.
- [5] Sarah Kenderdine. Pure Land: Inside the Mogao Grottoes at Dunghuang - Sarah Kenderdine — sarahkenderdine.info. <https://sarahkenderdine.info/installations-and-curated-exhibitions/pure-land-inside-the-mogao-grottoes-at-dunghuang>. [Accessed 28-Feb-2023].
- [6] Science Visualization Group at AMNH. Collectionscope — amnh-sciviz.github.io. <https://amnh-sciviz.github.io/collectionscope/>. [Accessed 28-Feb-2023].
- [7] Jianping Fan, Yuli Gao, and Hangzai Luo. Hierarchical classification for automatic image annotation. In *Proceedings of the 30th annual international*

- ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval*, pages 111–118, 2007.
- [8] Danilo M Eler, Marcel Y Nakazaki, Fernando V Paulovich, Davi P Santos, Gabriel F Andery, Maria Cristina F Oliveira, João Batista Neto, and Rosane Minghim. Visual analysis of image collections. *The Visual Computer*, 25:923–937, 2009.
- [9] Laurens Van der Maaten and Geoffrey Hinton. Visualizing data using t-sne. *Journal of machine learning research*, 9(11), 2008.
- [10] Leland McInnes, John Healy, and James Melville. Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1802.03426*, 2018.
- [11] Amit Sood. Every piece of art you’ve ever wanted to see – up close and searchable — ted.com. https://www.ted.com/talks/amit_sood_every_piece_of_art_you_ve_ever_wanted_to_see_up_close_and_searchable/transcript. [Accessed 15-Mar-2023].
- [12] Google. Google Arts Culture Experiments - t-SNE Map Experiment — artsexperiments.withgoogle.com. <https://artsexperiments.withgoogle.com/tsnemap/>. [Accessed 28-Feb-2023].
- [13] Refik Anadol. Archive Dreaming à AI Data Sculpture — refikanadol.com. <https://refikanadol.com/works/archive-dreaming/>. [Accessed 28-Feb-2023].
- [14] Audun M. Åygaard. Visualizing an art collection — auduno.com. <https://www.auduno.com/2018/10/27/visualizing-an-art-collection/>. [Accessed 28-Feb-2023].
- [15] Zeming Lin, Halil Akin, Roshan Rao, Brian Hie, Zhongkai Zhu, Wenting Lu, Nikita Smetanin, Robert Verkuil, Ori Kabeli, Yaniv Shmueli, et al. Evolutionary-scale prediction of atomic level protein structure with a language model. *bioRxiv*, pages 2022–07, 2022.
- [16] Zihou Ng. Exploring Fashion MNIST — stwind. <https://observablehq.com/@stwind/exploring-fashion-mnist>. [Accessed 28-Feb-2023].
- [17] Isabella di Lenardo, Benoît Laurent Auguste Seguin, and Frédéric Kaplan. Visual patterns discovery in large databases of paintings. Technical report, 2016.
- [18] Document embedding using UMAP x2014; umap 0.5 documentation — umap-learn.readthedocs.io. https://umap-learn.readthedocs.io/en/latest/document_embedding.html. [Accessed 07-Jun-2023].